

Web of Science, Scopus, and OpenAlex: A Comparative Bibliometric Analysis of Coverage, Disciplinary Profiles, and Database convergence

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Abstract

Web of Science and Scopus have dominated bibliometric analysis for two decades, but OpenAlex, launched in 2022 by OurResearch, challenges this duopoly through open infrastructure. This study compares the coverage, structural profiles, and overlap patterns of Web of Science (WoS), Scopus, and OpenAlex (2015–2024), analysing over 105 million records across five disciplinary areas through DOI-based matching and the OpenAlex Topics taxonomy. WoS and Scopus exhibit 95% overlap with nearly identical typological distributions and thematic profiles, functioning as homogeneous infrastructure primarily oriented toward STEM evaluation. OpenAlex doubles their combined coverage but presents notable limitations, as only 67% of its records receive thematic classification and systematic metadata inconsistencies persist. Anglophone bias is pronounced across all three platforms, with 96.2% of WoS records in English, compared to 90.8% in Scopus and 77.5% in OpenAlex. Disciplinary divergence is most acute in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), where only 31% of OpenAlex SSH records appear in WoS, versus 78% in Physical Sciences. OpenAlex indexes 21 million unique DOI-tagged records absent from commercial databases. No single infrastructure captures the totality of global scholarly output. The 95% WoS–Scopus overlap, combined with 21 million OpenAlex-exclusive records, reveals the structural fragmentation of the bibliographic ecosystem. Rigorous research evaluation therefore requires multi-source strategies that recognise the complementarity between commercial curation and open comprehensiveness

Keywords

Bibliometric analysis, Bibliographic databases, Web of Science, Scopus, OpenAlex, Coverage, Overlap, Research evaluation, Bibliographic infrastructure, Linguistic diversity

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1. Introduction

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57 The scholarly information landscape has undergone unprecedented transformation over the
58 past two decades, fundamentally altering how academic knowledge is produced, disseminated,
59 accessed, and evaluated. Bibliographic databases constitute the core information infrastructure,
60 as they determine which scholarly outputs are discoverable, how they are classified and
61 represented, and ultimately which knowledge counts in formal evaluation systems (Krüger &
62 Petersohn, 2023). For much of this period, Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus exerted near-
63 monopolistic control over bibliographic retrieval and bibliometric analysis, functioning as the
64 de facto infrastructure for research evaluation worldwide (Martín-Martín et al., 2021).
65 However, the current landscape is characterised by a multiplicity of information sources that
66 challenge this duopoly, particularly through the emergence of open bibliographic platforms
67 (Torres-Salinas et al., 2023).

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69 This transformation began with Google Scholar in 2004, which democratised access through
70 large-scale crawling and indexing of institutional repositories and open-access journals, and
71 other scholarly resources available on the web. A process that accelerated with the development
72 of regional databases such as SciELO and Dialnet. More recently, OpenAlex, launched in 2022
73 by OurResearch as the successor to Microsoft Academic Graph (Priem et al., 2022), has
74 positioned itself as a viable alternative by integrating heterogeneous sources including
75 Crossref, PubMed, ORCID, and institutional repositories under a CC0 licence (Forchino &
76 Torres-Salinas, 2026).

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78 This evolution is closely linked to research evaluation reforms, because the rise of open and
79 comprehensive infrastructures has broadened the empirical evidence base for assessment and
80 made evaluative practices less dependent on a single commercial source. Initiatives such as the
81 Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) in 2012 and the Leiden Manifesto
82 (Hicks et al., 2015) challenged the use of journal-level metrics as proxies for scientific
83 relevance. The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) in 2022 and the
84 Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (2024) have institutionalised this reform
85 movement, committing funding agencies to ground evaluation in open infrastructures. The
86 convergence between open scientific information infrastructures and evaluative reforms thus
87 creates a context in which democratisation of access is complemented by more contextualised
88 assessment of scholarly trajectories (Torres-Salinas et al., 2025).

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90 Despite their growing relevance, open bibliographic infrastructures remain affected by
91 unresolved issues of coverage, representativeness, and data quality. Existing studies document
92 coverage disparities (Culbert et al., 2025; Maddi et al., 2025), linguistic biases (Céspedes et
93 al., 2024), and metadata inconsistencies (Mongeon et al., 2025; Forchino & Torres-Salinas,
94 2026), but important empirical gaps persist regarding their disciplinary profiles, longitudinal
95 dynamics, and suitability for rigorous research evaluation. First, although studies have
96 compared overall volumes and overlap patterns, systematic analyses of thematic profiles,
97 longitudinal trends, and linguistic distributions remain scarce, particularly for recent periods
98 capturing OpenAlex's consolidation. Second, overlap analyses typically focus on aggregate
99 counts rather than examining convergence patterns across disciplines and document types,
100 limiting the granularity of recommendations. Third, uncertainties persist regarding metadata
101 quality in open platforms and their suitability for rigorous institutional evaluation. These gaps
102 carry significant implications for how scholarly knowledge is organised, retrieved, and
103 evaluated; the selection, structuring, and representation of scholarly records in each
104 infrastructure shape downstream retrieval, classification, and evaluative practices. To address
105 these gaps, this study pursues three specific objectives:

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107 1. Analyse the temporal evolution of scientific output indexed in Web of Science, Scopus,
108 and OpenAlex during the period 2015–2024, comparing absolute magnitudes and
109 quinquennial expansion dynamics.

110 2. Characterise the thematic profiles of each platform through analysis of typological
111 distribution, disciplinary composition across five areas (Social Sciences and
112 Humanities, SSH; Biomedical and Health Sciences, BHS; Physical Sciences and
113 Engineering, PSE; Life and Earth Sciences, LES; and Mathematics and Computer
114 Science, MCS), and linguistic diversity, identifying systematic biases toward particular
115 thematic areas and languages.

116 3. Quantify overlap between platforms through DOI-based matching, identifying the
117 shared corpus, binary intersections, exclusive content, and disciplinary convergence
118 patterns.

119 To our knowledge, this is the first large-scale comparative study of Web of Science, Scopus,
120 and OpenAlex to simultaneously examine coverage, disciplinary and linguistic profiles, and
121 DOI-based overlap patterns. Previous research has often examined these dimensions
122 separately, using different scopes, periods, or methodological criteria. By analyzing them
123 together, this study offers a more contextualized account of where the three infrastructures
124 converge, where they diverge, and what these differences imply for database selection. The
125 results are therefore relevant not only for bibliometricians and data specialists, but also for
126 research managers, evaluation agencies, and institutional decision-makers seeking to make
127 informed choices about the use of bibliographic data in evaluation and policy contexts.

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129 The manuscript is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on bibliographic
130 database evaluation. Section 3 details the methodology of the study. After that, Section 4
131 presents the results, focusing on temporal coverage, structural profiles, disciplinary and
132 linguistic distributions, and cross-database overlap. Finally, Section 5 discusses the main
133 implications of the findings.

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136 **2. Literature review**

137 While the literature on bibliographic database evaluation is extensive, this review focuses
138 specifically on Web of Science, Scopus, and OpenAlex. The section is organised into two parts.
139 The first examines differences in coverage and representation, including how each database
140 captures journals, disciplines, languages, and publication models. The second focuses on
141 metadata quality and reliability, addressing the consistency and completeness of the
142 information provided by each infrastructure. Together, these sections identify the main
143 strengths, limitations, and biases of the three platforms.

144 **2.1. Database coverage and linguistic-disciplinary biases**

145 Comparative coverage analysis reveals structural patterns with direct methodological
146 implications for research evaluation. Gusenbauer (2024), examining the disciplinary coverage
147 of 56 databases, established that coverage divergence is both structurally systematic and
148 disciplinarily heterogeneous. This finding was corroborated at scale by Culbert et al. (2025),
149 who document that Web of Science and Scopus share 90% of their content, a convergence
150 already identified at journal level by Mongeon and Paul-Hus (2016), contrasting with
151 OpenAlex's markedly broader reach. For the period 2015–2022, the shared corpus among all
152 three platforms, restricted to records with valid DOIs, represents 74% of WoS, 60% of Scopus,

153 and only 21% of OpenAlex, while OpenAlex indexes 78.2% of its content exclusively
154 (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). These differences reflect divergent editorial models. WoS and
155 Scopus implement selective curation through editorial committees, whereas OpenAlex adopts
156 a comprehensive harvesting strategy drawing on heterogeneous sources including Crossref,
157 PubMed, and institutional repositories.

158 At the disciplinary level, coverage asymmetries become more pronounced. Gallardo and
159 Bruccoleri (2024), analysing Argentine publications, find that 42.4% of records appear in both
160 Scopus and OpenAlex, 35.9% exclusively in OpenAlex, and only 7.1% solely in Scopus, with
161 disciplinary divergence particularly acute in Social Sciences, where Scopus captures only
162 25.7% of OpenAlex records versus 70.1% in Physical Sciences. Delgado-Quirós et al. (2024)
163 identify the structural mechanisms underlying these absences, documenting that editorial
164 selectivity and language requirements account for most missing publications in WoS and
165 Scopus.

166 These coverage gaps are compounded by the limited representation of open-access journals in
167 commercial databases. Maddi et al. (2025) document that OpenAlex indexes 54.6% of active
168 resources from the ROAD directory, compared to only 9.8–11.7% in WoS and Scopus. Khanna
169 et al. (2022) demonstrate that Open Journal Systems journals, 79.9% of which are in the Global
170 South and 84.2% of which operate under diamond open-access models, achieve indexing rates
171 of 1.2–5.7% in commercial databases versus 63.8% in OpenAlex. Simard et al. (2024) confirm
172 that OpenAlex indexes 87% of active diamond journals from DOAJ, compared to 5% in WoS
173 Core Collection and 28% in Scopus, with 6,811 diamond journals appearing exclusively in
174 OpenAlex. Taken together, these figures suggest that the selective curation criteria of
175 commercial databases systematically disadvantage regional and multilingual publication
176 models (Alonso-Álvarez & Eck, 2025; Simard et al., 2024).

177 The linguistic dimension reinforces and deepens this picture of structural inequality. Céspedes
178 et al. (2024) document that WoS and Scopus concentrate over 95% of their corpus in English,
179 with representation below 1% for Spanish, Chinese, French, German, Russian, and Japanese.
180 OpenAlex presents a more diverse distribution, with approximately 75% English according to
181 declared metadata and 68% after manual correction, alongside notable proportions of Chinese
182 (4.2%), Spanish (2.6%), Russian (2.0%), and Japanese (1.3%). However, this greater diversity
183 comes with a significant caveat. That is, automated language inference based on titles and
184 abstracts generates systematic misclassification errors, with 5.5 million Chinese articles and 4
185 million Russian articles incorrectly labelled as English publications, while the inverse error
186 remains marginal. This asymmetry is reflected in language-differentiated precision rates, where
187 Chinese achieves only 63.7% precision compared to over 90% for Spanish and Portuguese, a
188 performance differential attributable to the synergy between OpenAlex and open regional
189 infrastructures such as SciELO, Redalyc, and Latindex.

190 **2.2. Metadata quality and reliability**

191 Reference coverage limitations constitute a critical dimension differentiating indexing
192 architectures. Culbert et al. (2025) document that WoS and Scopus record averages of 6.4 and
193 6.2 additional references per article, respectively, compared with OpenAlex, a differential
194 concentrated in grey literature and incompletely normalized citations. Gusenbauer (2024) finds
195 that OpenAlex systematically underestimates 23.9% of actual references, versus errors below
196 3% in commercial databases, because OpenAlex counts only references with structured
197 metadata available in open sources, primarily harvested through Crossref (Hendricks et al.,

198 2020), whereas WoS and Scopus integrate broader indexing procedures with manual validation
199 across diverse document typologies. This disciplinary bias is particularly pronounced in areas
200 with greater dependence on grey literature, such as Social Sciences and Applied Engineering,
201 where underestimation in OpenAlex limits exhaustiveness for systematic reviews.

202 Metadata quality is a determining factor in database selection, involving trade-offs between
203 coverage breadth and classificatory precision (Arroyo-Machado, 2024). While WoS and
204 Scopus prioritize controlled curation, OpenAlex privileges exhaustiveness over accuracy,
205 affecting classification consistency across document types. Haupka et al. (2024) document that
206 OpenAlex maintains less granular typological classification than commercial databases
207 following methodological updates in 2024. Mongeon et al. (2025), analyzing 6.6 million
208 records with matching DOIs (2021–2023), identify that 93.5% of discrepancies in article and
209 review classification correspond to errors in OpenAlex, alongside inconsistencies in
210 publication year (8.1% of cases) and language attribution (93.9% of errors attributable to
211 OpenAlex incorrectly labeling non-English publications as English). Nevertheless, Cebrian et
212 al. (2025) detect no significant differences between databases in health sciences, pointing that
213 OpenAlex metadata quality varies considerably across disciplinary domains.

214 Beyond classification errors, differential completeness of specific metadata fields introduces
215 additional analytical biases. Culbert et al. (2025) identify asymmetric DOI availability across
216 platforms, with 4.2 million records lacking a DOI in WoS, 2.6 million in Scopus, and 21.7
217 million in OpenAlex. In the shared corpus, WoS and Scopus include abstracts in over 92% of
218 articles versus 87% in OpenAlex. Forchino and Torres-Salinas (2026) report that 61.5% of
219 OpenAlex records lack institutional affiliation, alongside partial identification of retractions
220 relative to Retraction Watch, the presence of duplicates, errors in citation assignment, and gaps
221 in bibliographic metadata. These limitations require additional validation routines when
222 OpenAlex is employed as the primary source for institutional evaluation.

223 3. Methods

224 The study follows a four-step analytical workflow:

- 225 1. **Data extraction:** large-scale retrieval from Web of Science Core Collection, Scopus,
226 and OpenAlex.
- 227 2. **Corpus definition:** restriction to articles, reviews, and letters (2015–2024), with
228 deduplication and metadata cleaning.
- 229 3. **Thematic classification:** DOI-based matching against the OpenAlex Topics taxonomy
230 across five disciplinary areas.
- 231 4. **Overlap analysis:** cross-database comparison based on valid, normalized DOIs.

232 Data were extracted from Web of Science Core Collection and Scopus via the InCites and
233 SciVal platforms respectively, and from a complete snapshot of OpenAlex, all retrieved in
234 August 2025. Records were partitioned by publication year, document type, and open access
235 status to ensure retrieval completeness, and deduplicated using proprietary identifiers (UT in
236 Web of Science, EID in Scopus). The corpus was restricted to articles, reviews, and letters;
237 book chapters and conference proceedings were excluded from Web of Science, and preprints,
238 datasets, and non-comparable document types from OpenAlex. This yielded 23,935,480
239 records from Web of Science, 27,329,548 from Scopus, and 54,139,961 from OpenAlex.

240 *Table 1. Corpus characterization by database (2015-2024)*

Database	Total retrieved	With unique DOI *	With unique DOI (%)	Thematic Classified	Classified * (%)
Web of Science	23.935.480	22.802.830	95.3%	21.733.235	90.8%
Scopus	27.329.548	25.891.438	94.7%	23.500.613	86.0%
OpenAlex	54.139.961	46.278.539	85.5%	36.150.302	66.8%

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242 * With unique DOI: records with a valid, normalized DOI after deduplication; this subset constitutes the
243 matchable corpus for cross-database overlap analysis. ** Classified (%): share of total retrieved records with
244 an OpenAlex Topic (Thematic Classified records).
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246 DOI availability constitutes the technical precondition for cross-database comparison. Valid
247 DOIs were present in 95.3% of Web of Science records, 94.7% of Scopus records, and 85.5%
248 of OpenAlex records, with the lowest rates in Social Sciences and Humanities (91–96%) and
249 the highest in Physical Sciences and Engineering and related areas (above 97%). Records
250 lacking a valid DOI were retained for internal descriptive analyses but excluded from cross-
251 platform overlap analysis.

252 All records were assigned to a common thematic framework based on the OpenAlex Topics
253 taxonomy, covering five macro-level areas: Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH),
254 Biomedical and Health Sciences (BHS), Physical Sciences and Engineering (PSE), Life and
255 Earth Sciences (LES), and Mathematics and Computer Science (MCS). For Web of Science
256 and Scopus, assignment was performed via DOI-based matching against this taxonomy; for
257 OpenAlex, the native Topics classification was applied directly. The unclassified fraction
258 among DOI-bearing records reached 4.7% in WoS and 9.3% in Scopus, comprising DOIs
259 lacking an assigned topic in OpenAlex and DOIs absent from OpenAlex entirely.

260 Metadata cleaning and standardization were performed in Python 3.13, incorporating DOI
261 normalization, duplicate control, and verification of mandatory fields. Visualizations were
262 generated in R 4.5.1. Table 2 summarizes the six analytical components, procedures, and
263 research objectives addressed in this study.

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265 *Table 2. Summary of analytical components and associated research objective*

Analytical component	Procedure	Study objective
Temporal evolution	Annual volumes; quinquennial comparison 2015–19 vs. 2020–24	Obj. 1 — Coverage and growth dynamics
Document type distribution	Proportional breakdown of articles, reviews, and letters by quinquennium	Obj. 2 — Structural profiles
Disciplinary coverage	Distribution across five thematic areas (SSH, BHS, PSE, LES, MCS)	Obj. 2 — Structural profiles
Linguistic diversity	Comparative language rankings by absolute volume	Obj. 2 — Structural profiles
Cross-database overlap	DOI-based matching: shared corpus, binary intersections, exclusive content	Obj. 3 — Overlap and convergence
Disciplinary overlap	Overlap disaggregated by thematic area	Obj. 3 — Overlap and convergence

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268 **4. Results**

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270 **4.1. Temporal coverage and growth dynamics**

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272 Temporal evolution from 2015 to 2024 reveals substantial differences in absolute volumes and
 273 quinquennial dynamics among the three platforms (Table 3). Web of Science and Scopus
 274 register growth of 35.1% and 35.2% respectively between the quinquennia 2015–2019 and
 275 2020–2024, reaching cumulative totals of 23.9 and 27.3 million records. OpenAlex presents
 276 markedly lower quinquennial variation (6.2%), with a cumulative total of 54.1 million records,
 277 approximately double the combined output of the two commercial platforms. Scopus
 278 consistently maintains approximately 340,000 additional records per year compared to Web of
 279 Science, reflecting its broader journal coverage policy.

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281 Growth trajectories across the decade are not uniform. Web of Science and Scopus exhibit
 282 parallel annual patterns throughout the period, while OpenAlex shows greater interannual
 283 variability, including an 8.3% contraction in 2022 that reduced its corpus by 471,287 records,
 284 likely attributable to retrospective deduplication and harvesting adjustments in the platform's
 285 early consolidation phase. Both commercial databases present a moderate contraction in 2023
 286 (-3.1% in WoS, -1.9% in Scopus), followed by recovery in 2024 (+8.5% and +8.2%
 287 respectively), a pattern also observed in OpenAlex (+6.4%). Throughout the entire period,
 288 relative proportions among the three platforms remain stable, with OpenAlex consistently
 289 representing 52% of the combined volume, Scopus 25%, and Web of Science 21%.

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Table 3. Coverage and growth indicators by database, 2015-2024

Indicator	Web of Science	Scopus	OpenAlex
Quinquennium 1 (2015-19)	10.182.753	11.621.294	26.261.876
Quinquennium 2 (2020-24)	13.752.727	15.708.254	27.878.085
Q2/Q1 Growth	+35,1%	+35,2%	+6,2%
Total 2015-2024	23.935.480	27.329.548	54.139.961
Annual Average	2.393.548	2.732.955	5.413.996
Total growth from 2015 to 2024	+59,7%	+57,1%	+8,1%

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293 **4.2. Comparative structural profiles**

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295 Document type distribution for 2015–2024 (Table 4) reveals a comparable structure between
 296 Web of Science and Scopus, with articles accounting for 90–91% of records, reviews for 7–
 297 8%, and letters for 2%. OpenAlex presents a more concentrated distribution, with articles
 298 representing 95% of its corpus, reviews 3%, and letters 1%. Quinquennial analysis shows
 299 stability in Scopus across both periods (90% articles), while Web of Science registers a
 300 moderate increase in reviews from 6% to 8% between 2015–2019 and 2020–2024. OpenAlex
 301 shows a slight contraction in articles (96% to 95%) with marginal growth in reviews (3% to
 302 4%), with letters remaining stable at 1% across both quinquennia.

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Table 4. Distribution by document type and database. Quinquennial and total values, 2015-2024

Document Type	Quinquennium	Web of Science		Scopus		OpenAlex	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Article	2015-2019	9.321.194	92	10.493.146	90	25.207.080	96

	2020-2024	12.414.344	90	14.190.676	90	26.447.722	95
	<i>Change</i>		<i>-2 pp</i>		<i>0 pp</i>		<i>-1 pp</i>
	Total 2015-24	21.735.538	91	24.683.822	90	51.654.802	95
Review	2015-2019	621.343	6	886.970	8	742.411	3
	2020-2024	1.057.965	8	1.239.093	8	1.135.571	4
	<i>Change</i>		<i>+2 pp</i>		<i>0 pp</i>		<i>+1 pp</i>
	Total 2015-24	1.679.308	7	2.126.063	8	1.877.982	3
Letter	2015-2019	240.216	2	241.178	2	312.385	1
	2020-2024	280.418	2	278.485	2	294.792	1
	<i>Change</i>		<i>0 pp</i>		<i>0 pp</i>		<i>0 pp</i>
	Total 2015-24	520.634	2	519.663	2	607.177	1
TOTAL		23.935.480	100	27.329.548	100	54.139.961	100

305 *pp* = percentage points. Changes represent differences between quinquennia 2020-2024 and 2015-2019.

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Beyond document type, the three platforms also diverge in their disciplinary composition (Fig. 1). Thematic distribution for 2015–2024 shows that Web of Science and Scopus present closely aligned profiles across all five areas, with Biomedical and Health Sciences (BHS) dominating both platforms in nearly identical proportions (37.4% in WoS; 37.5% in Scopus), followed by Physical Sciences and Engineering (PSE), Life and Earth Sciences (LES), and Mathematics and Computer Science (MCS) in comparable shares, and a difference of only one percentage point in Social Sciences and Humanities (10.1% in WoS; 11.1% in Scopus). OpenAlex, by contrast, presents a markedly differentiated profile. Although BHS remains the dominant area, its relative weight decreases to 34.5%, while SSH rises to 20.4% of the total classified corpus, nearly double its share in Scopus and more than double its share in WoS, accompanied by somewhat lower participation of PSE and slightly higher participation of MCS.

Disciplinary divergence is further compounded by differences in linguistic composition (Table 5). English concentration reaches 96.2% in Web of Science, 90.8% in Scopus, and 77.5% in OpenAlex, with non-English languages accounting for 3.8%, 9.2%, and 22.5% of each corpus respectively. Among non-English languages, Spanish ranks second in WoS (1.1%; 262,823 records) and third in Scopus (1.0%; 273,381 records), and second in OpenAlex (2.8%; 1,538,448 records). Chinese presents a divergent pattern across platforms, ranking sixth in WoS (0.4%; 87,605 records), second in Scopus (4.4%; 1,209,576 records), and tenth in OpenAlex (1.1%; 615,529 records). Indonesian ranks third in OpenAlex (2.4%; 1,316,175 records), a position it does not occupy in either commercial database. Russian and Portuguese maintain intermediate rankings across all three platforms, while Japanese registers a notably higher presence in OpenAlex (2.0%; 1,077,495 records) than in WoS (0.3%; 83,265 records) or Scopus (0.3%; 91,341 records).

Fig. 1. Absolute and percentage distribution of classified research Areas in Web of Science, Scopus, and OpenAlex, 2015-2024

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Table 5: Linguistic Distribution in Web of Science, Scopus, and OpenAlex, 2015-2024

Rank	Web of Science			Scopus			OpenAlex		
	Language	n	%	Language	n	%	Language	n	%
1	English	23,022,125	96.2	English	24,826,757	90.8	English	41,969,376	77.5
2	Spanish	262,823	1.1	Chinese	1,209,576	4.4	Spanish	1,538,448	2.8
3	Russian	117,226	0.5	Spanish	273,381	1	Indonesian	1,316,175	2.4
4	German	103,343	0.4	Russian	254,843	0.9	Portuguese	1,241,305	2.3
5	Portuguese	101,569	0.4	German	158,368	0.6	Russian	1,177,851	2.2
6	Chinese	87,605	0.4	French	127,461	0.5	Japanese	1,077,495	2
7	French	83,265	0.3	Portuguese	91,341	0.3	French	831,300	1.5
8	Italian	34,716	0.1	Japanese	76,222	0.3	German	787,067	1.5
9	Turkish	25,622	0.1	Italian	51,961	0.2	Korean	735,917	1.4
10	Korean	18,370	0.1	Korean	39,255	0.1	Chinese	615,529	1.1
<i>Other languages</i>	<i>60</i>	<i>76,262</i>	<i>0.3</i>	<i>54</i>	<i>219,649</i>	<i>0.8</i>	<i>44</i>	<i>2,217,242</i>	<i>4.1</i>
<i>No data</i>		<i>2,554</i>	<i>0</i>		<i>734</i>	<i>0</i>		<i>632,256</i>	<i>1.2</i>
TOTAL		23,935,480	100	Total	27,329,548	100	Total	54,139,961	100

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Note. Rankings based on absolute volume within each database. "Missing data" includes records without language metadata, null values, or inconsistencies. Aggregate categories in italics

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4.3. Overlap and convergence patterns

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Overlap analysis is based on 22,802,830 unique DOIs in Web of Science (95.3% of its total corpus), 25,891,438 in Scopus (94.7%), and 46,278,539 in OpenAlex (85.5%), as reported in Table 1. DOI availability is lowest in Social Sciences and Humanities across all three platforms (91.9–96.0%). The shared core of records present simultaneously in all three databases comprises approximately 21 million documents, representing 92.2% of the Web of Science corpus with valid DOI, 81.2% of Scopus, and 45.4% of OpenAlex. Pairwise convergence

349 between Web of Science and Scopus is high, as 95% of WoS records appear in Scopus, and
 350 83% of Scopus records appear in WoS (Table 6).

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Table 6. Pairwise overlap between databases based on original data

Records from database in row ↓ present in database in column →	Web of Science	Scopus	Openalex
Web of Science		21.577.226 95% from WoS in Scopus	22.100.052 97% from WoS in OpenAlex
Scopus	21.577.226 83% from Scopus in WoS		24.080.729 94% from Scopus in OpenAlex
OpenAlex	22.100.052 48% from OpenAlex in WoS	24.080.729 52% from OpenAlex in Scopus	

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Fig. 2. Proportional overlap among Web of Science, Scopus, and OpenAlex through DOI-based matching, 2015-202

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Note. Circle sizes are proportional to the total number of records with DOI in each database (OpenAlex 46.2M, Scopus 25.8M, WoS 22.8M). Values represent percentages of each database's total. Percentages represent share of each database's total DOI corpus

368 OpenAlex presents a markedly different pattern. Although 97% of WoS records and 94% of
 369 Scopus records are indexed in OpenAlex, only 48% of OpenAlex's DOI-bearing corpus appears
 370 in WoS and 52% in Scopus, indicating that OpenAlex indexes approximately 21 million unique
 371 records with valid DOI not present in either commercial database. Web of Science is the
 372 platform with the lowest volume of exclusive records, with 158,794 DOI-tagged documents
 373 absent from both other databases (Fig. 2).

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375 Disaggregated analysis by disciplinary area (Table 7) reveals that convergence between
 376 databases is disciplinarily heterogeneous. Web of Science and Scopus maintain high and stable
 377 overlap across all five areas, with at least 87% of WoS records present in Scopus in every
 378 discipline, reaching maximum values in Physical Sciences and Engineering and Life and Earth
 379 Sciences, where DOI adoption is virtually universal. The proportion of Scopus records present
 380 in WoS ranges from 75% in SSH to 95% in PSE, reflecting Scopus's marginally broader
 381 coverage across all disciplines, most pronounced in social sciences. OpenAlex presents
 382 maximum divergence in Social Sciences and Humanities: only 31% of its SSH records with
 383 valid DOI appear in WoS and 37% in Scopus, compared to values of 63–82% in the remaining
 384 disciplinary areas.

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386
387 *Table 7: Pairwise database overlap by disciplinary area*

Records from database in row ↓ present in database in column →	Web of Science	Scopus
Web of Science		SSH - 90%
		BHS - 95%
		PSE - 98%
		LES - 97%
		MCS - 96%
		from WoS in Scopus
Scopus	SSH - 75%	
	BHS - 88%	
	PSE - 95%	
	LES - 90%	
	MCS - 89%	
	from Scopus in WoS	
OpenAlex	SSH - 31%	SSH - 37%
	BHS - 66%	BHS - 72%
	PSE - 79%	PSE - 82%
	LES - 69%	LES - 75%
	MCS - 63%	MCS - 69%
	From OpenAlex in WoS	de OpenAlex in Scopus

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410 *Notes: (1) Overlaps from WoS or Scopus into OpenAlex are not reported, as they are equal to 100% by*
 411 *construction of the DOI-bridge discipline assignment. (2) SSH = Social Sciences & Humanities; BHS =*
 412 *Biomedical & Health Sciences; PSE = Physical Sciences & Engineering; LES = Life & Earth Sciences; MCS =*
 413 *Mathematics & Computer Science. Bold values indicate maximum divergences.*

414 415 416 **5. Discussion**

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418 The results confirm and extend previous findings on the structural differentiation of the three
 419 major bibliographic infrastructures. The 95% overlap between Web of Science and Scopus at
 420 the record level, combined with virtually identical disciplinary and typological distributions,
 421 supports the characterization of both platforms as functionally interchangeable for STEM-
 422 oriented bibliometric analysis, consistent with findings by Culbert et al. (2025) and the journal-
 423 level convergence documented by Mongeon and Paul-Hus (2016). This convergence is stable
 424 across all five disciplinary areas and both quinquennia analyzed. For institutional evaluation
 425 purposes, selecting one or the other commercial database introduces minimal substantive
 426 differences in coverage or composition across Biomedical, Physical, and Life Sciences,
 427 although Scopus maintains a systematically larger corpus of approximately 340,000 additional

428 records per year, a difference that may acquire relevance in evaluations sensitive to absolute
429 counts.

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431 The situation differs substantially in Social Sciences and Humanities. The gap between
432 OpenAlex (20.4% SSH) and WoS (10.1%) or Scopus (11.1%) is not a marginal discrepancy
433 but a structural difference rooted in divergent indexing logics, consistent with the disciplinary
434 asymmetries documented by Gallardo and Bruccoleri (2024) for Argentine publications and by
435 Delgado-Quirós et al. (2024), who identify editorial selectivity and language requirements as
436 the primary mechanisms behind missing publications in commercial databases. That only 31%
437 of OpenAlex SSH records with valid DOI appear in WoS, compared to 78% in Physical
438 Sciences, quantifies the scale of this divergence and its disciplinary specificity at a level of
439 granularity not previously reported in the literature. The 21 million records indexed exclusively
440 in OpenAlex, concentrated disproportionately in SSH and non-English languages, represent a
441 segment of global scholarly output that remains systematically invisible to commercial
442 evaluation infrastructures, extending the findings of Simard et al. (2024) on diamond journal
443 coverage and of Maddi et al. (2025) on open-access repository indexing. This finding is
444 particularly relevant in the context of ongoing research evaluation reforms promoted by
445 CoARA which explicitly call for evaluation systems grounded in open and inclusive
446 bibliographic infrastructures (Torres-Salinas et al., 2025).

447

448 Linguistic diversity data reinforce this asymmetry. The 96.2% English concentration in WoS
449 and 90.8% in Scopus contrast with 77.5% in OpenAlex, a differential consistent with the
450 structural Anglophone bias documented by Céspedes et al. (2024), who report values of over
451 95% English in commercial databases and approximately 68–75% in OpenAlex after metadata
452 correction. The notable presence of Indonesian as the third most represented language in
453 OpenAlex (2.4%; 1,316,175 records) and the divergent ranking of Chinese across platforms
454 reflect fundamentally different harvesting strategies rather than differences in actual scientific
455 output. These patterns are consistent with the precision asymmetries identified by Céspedes et
456 al. (2024), who document that Chinese achieves only 63.7% language attribution precision in
457 OpenAlex compared to over 90% for Spanish and Portuguese, a differential attributable to the
458 synergy between OpenAlex and Ibero-American open regional infrastructures such as SciELO,
459 Redalyc, and Latindex.

460

461 Metadata quality constitutes an additional axis of differentiation with practical consequences
462 for analytical reliability. The lower DOI coverage in OpenAlex (85.5% versus 95.3% in WoS
463 and 94.7% in Scopus), the 66.8% thematic classification rate, and the documented
464 inconsistencies in language attribution and institutional affiliation corroborate the findings of
465 Mongeon et al. (2025) and Forchino and Torres-Salinas (2026), who identify OpenAlex as the
466 primary source of classification errors in cross-database comparisons. These limitations are
467 disciplinarily heterogeneous: metadata quality in OpenAlex is more reliable in biomedical and
468 physical sciences, where DOI adoption is near-universal and thematic classification rates are
469 higher, than in SSH, where both coverage and classification gaps are most acute, in line with
470 the disciplinary heterogeneity reported by Cebrián et al. (2025). The 8.3% contraction observed
471 in OpenAlex in 2022, attributable to retrospective deduplication and harvesting adjustments,
472 further illustrates the platform's ongoing consolidation and the need to account for temporal
473 instability when using OpenAlex snapshots for longitudinal analysis.

474

475 These findings collectively demonstrate that the choice of bibliographic infrastructure is not a
476 neutral technical decision but one with direct consequences for what counts as science in
477 evaluation contexts. The complementarity between commercial curation and open

478 comprehensiveness is empirically grounded: WoS and Scopus offer precision and metadata
 479 reliability at the cost of coverage breadth and linguistic inclusivity, while OpenAlex offers
 480 unmatched reach at the cost of classificatory consistency. Multi-source strategies that combine
 481 both types of infrastructure are not merely advisable but empirically necessary for any
 482 evaluation framework aspiring to represent the full diversity of global scholarly output, a
 483 recommendation aligned with the positions of Alonso-Álvarez and Eck (2025) and Khanna et
 484 al. (2022) on the structural underrepresentation of non-commercial publication models in
 485 global science metrics. Table 8 synthesizes the key strengths and limitations of each platform
 486 across the four analytical dimensions examined in this study.

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 489 *Table 8: Strategic recommendations for database Selection by use context*

Use Case	Recommended Database(s)	Justification
STEM/biomedical analysis	WoS or Scopus (interchangeable)	87-97% overlap in these disciplines; prefer WoS if integration with Journal Citation Reports is required
SSH/multilingual analysis	OpenAlex (essential)	Triples SSH representation (20% vs. 9% WoS); covers 63.8% OJS journals vs. 1.2-5.7% commercial databases; multiplies Spanish coverage by 5.8 and Portuguese by 12.2
Institutional rankings and aggregate evaluations	WoS + Scopus + OpenAlex (mandatory combination)	Avoids exclusion of 21 million unique OpenAlex records (45.5% of its corpus); mitigates disciplinary and linguistic biases; requires rigorous deduplication protocols
Collaboration network analysis	OpenAlex (technical advantages)	Open data under CC0 license; broader affiliation coverage in non-hegemonic regions; unrestricted REST API access
Individual evaluation with career consequences	Mandatory manual verification independent of database	36.5% of journals in Cabell's Predatory Reports catalogue indexed in OpenAlex (Donner, 2025); requires case-by-case validation for accreditations, promotions, and competitions

490 *Note. SSH = Social Sciences and Humanities; OJS = Open Journal Systems; CC0 = Creative Commons Zero (public domain*
 491 *dedication). Recommendations based on empirical evidence from disciplinary overlap analysis (Table 6), linguistic diversity*
 492 *(Table 4), and documented metadata quality issues. "Interchangeable" indicates >90% convergence; "essential" indicates*
 493 *>50% unique content; "mandatory" indicates complementarity required to avoid systematic exclusion.*
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495 These results should nevertheless be interpreted in light of certain methodological
 496 considerations. The use of the OpenAlex Topics taxonomy as a common classification
 497 framework facilitates comparison across the three platforms, but also makes the disciplinary
 498 profiles of Web of Science and Scopus partly dependent on OpenAlex's classification logic.
 499 Similarly, DOI-based matching provides a robust basis for overlap analysis, yet it excludes
 500 records without valid DOIs, a limitation that is especially relevant in Social Sciences and
 501 Humanities and in regional or non-English publication venues. The analysis is also based on
 502 database snapshots retrieved in August 2025. This is particularly relevant for OpenAlex, which
 503 has undergone rapid development and frequent structural updates; subsequent retrospective
 504 indexing, deduplication, reclassification, or metadata corrections may therefore modify record
 505 counts, disciplinary assignments, and overlap patterns.

506 507 **6. Data availability statement**

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 509 The OpenAlex data used in this study were obtained from a publicly available snapshot
 510 downloaded in August 2025 (<https://openalex.org/>). Web of Science and Scopus data were
 511 retrieved via institutional licenses through InCites and SciVal, respectively, and are subject to
 512 the terms and conditions of those platforms; these data cannot be made publicly available. The

513 analytical code used for data cleaning, DOI normalization, and overlap computation (Python
514 3.13) and for visualization (R 4.5.1) is available from the corresponding author upon request.

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517 7. References

518

519 Alonso-Alvarez, P., & van Eck, N. J. (2024). *Coverage and metadata completeness and*
520 *accuracy of African research publications in OpenAlex: A comparative analysis* (Versión
521 3). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2409.01120>

522 Arentoft, M., Berghmans, S., Borrell-Damian, L., Bottaro, S., Faure, J.-E., Gaillard, V., Glinos,
523 K., Albacete, J. L., Morais, R., Morris, J., Schiltz, M., & Stroobants, K. (2022). *Agreement*
524 *on Reforming Research Assessment*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13480728>

525 Arroyo-Machado, W. (2024). *Fuentes Bibliométricas: Guía Práctica de Selección y Uso* (1st
526 ed). Editorial UOC.

527 Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, Kramer, B., Neylon, C., & Waltman, L.
528 (2024). *Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information*.
529 <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10958522>

530 Cebrian, G., Borrego, Á., & Abadal, E. (2025). OpenAlex y Crossref como fuentes de datos
531 bibliográficas alternativas a Web of Science y Scopus en ciencias de la salud. *Revista*
532 *Española de Documentación Científica*, 48(1), 1649.
533 <https://doi.org/10.3989/redc.2025.1.1649>

534 Céspedes, L., Kozłowski, D., Pradier, C., Sainte-Marie, M. H., Shokida, N. S., Benz, P., Poitras,
535 C., Ninkov, A. B., Ebrahimi, S., Ayeni, P., Filali, S., Li, B., & Larivière, V. (2024).
536 *Evaluating the Linguistic Coverage of OpenAlex: An Assessment of Metadata Accuracy*
537 *and Completeness* (Versión 2). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2409.10633>

538 Culbert, J. H., Hobert, A., Jahn, N., Haupka, N., Schmidt, M., Donner, P., & Mayr, P. (2025).
539 Reference coverage analysis of OpenAlex compared to Web of Science and Scopus.
540 *Scientometrics*, 130(4), 2475-2492. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-025-05293-3>

541 (Declaration On Research Assessment), D., & Pardal-Peláez, B. (2018). Declaración de San
542 Francisco sobre la evaluación de la investigación. *Revista ORL*, 9(4), 295.
543 <https://doi.org/10.14201/orl.17845>

544 Delgado-Quirós, L., Aguillo, I. F., Martín-Martín, A., López-Cózar, E. D., Orduña-Malea, E.,
545 & Ortega, J. L. (2024). Why are these publications missing? Uncovering the reasons
546 behind the exclusion of documents in free-access scholarly databases. *Journal of the*
547 *Association for Information Science and Technology*, 75(1), 43-58.
548 <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24839>

549 Donner, P. (2025, junio 3). *Prevalence of predatory journals in OpenAlex*. [https://www.open-](https://www.open-bibliometrics.de/posts/20250603-QuestionableJournals/)
550 [bibliometrics.de/posts/20250603-QuestionableJournals/](https://www.open-bibliometrics.de/posts/20250603-QuestionableJournals/)

551 Forchino, M. V., & Torres-Salinas, D. (2026). The OpenAlex database in review: Evaluating
552 its applications, capabilities, and limitations. *Journal of Informetrics*, 20(2), 101800.
553 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2026.101800>

554 Gallardo, O., & Bruccoleri Ochoa, M. (2024). El problema de las bases de datos en la evaluación
555 de la producción científica en América Latina. Una exploración del potencial de OpenAlex
556 para las universidades argentinas. *Discursos del Sur, revista de teoría crítica en Ciencias*
557 *Sociales*, (13), 63-85. <https://doi.org/10.15381/dds.n13.27890>

558 Gusenbauer, M. (2024). Beyond Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science: An evaluation
559 of the backward and forward citation coverage of 59 databases' citation indices. *Research*
560 *Synthesis Methods*, 15(5), 802-817. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1729>

561 Haupka, N., Dörner, S., & Jahn, N. (2024). *Scholarly Communication Analytics: Recent*
562 *Changes in Document type classification in OpenAlex compared to Web of Science and*
563 *Scopus*. [https://subugoe.github.io/scholcomm_](https://subugoe.github.io/scholcomm_analytics/posts/openalex_document_types/)
[analytics/posts/openalex_document_types/](https://subugoe.github.io/scholcomm_analytics/posts/openalex_document_types/)

- 564 Hendricks, G., Tkaczyk, D., Lin, J., & Feeney, P. (2020). Crossref: The sustainable source of
565 community-owned scholarly metadata. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(1), 414-427.
566 https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00022
- 567 Hicks, D., Wouters, P., Waltman, L., De Rijcke, S., & Rafols, I. (2015). Bibliometrics: The
568 Leiden Manifesto for research metrics. *Nature*, 520(7548), 429-431.
569 <https://doi.org/10.1038/520429a>
- 570 Khanna, S., Ball, J., Alperin, J. P., & Willinsky, J. (2022). Recalibrating the scope of scholarly
571 publishing: A modest step in a vast decolonization process. *Quantitative Science Studies*,
572 3(4), 912-930. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00228
- 573 Krüger, A. K., & Petersohn, S. (2023). 'I want to be able to do what I know the tools will
574 allow us to do': Practicing evaluative bibliometrics through digital infrastructure.
575 *Research Evaluation*, 31(4), 475-485. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvac009>
- 576 Maddi, A., Maisonobe, M., & Boukacem-Zeghmouri, C. (2025). Geographical and disciplinary
577 coverage of open access journals: OpenAlex, Scopus, and WoS. *PLOS ONE*, 20(4),
578 e0320347. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0320347>
- 579 Martín-Martín, A., Thelwall, M., Orduna-Malea, E., & Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2021).
580 Google Scholar, Microsoft Academic, Scopus, Dimensions, Web of Science, and
581 OpenCitations' COCI: A multidisciplinary comparison of coverage via citations.
582 *Scientometrics*, 126(1), 871-906. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03690-4>
- 583 Mongeon, P., Hare, M., Riddle, P., Wilson, S., Krause, G., Marjoram, R., & Toupin, R. (2025).
584 *Investigating Document Type, Language, Publication Year, and Author Count*
585 *Discrepancies Between OpenAlex and Web of Science* (Versión 1). arXiv.
586 <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2508.18620>
- 587 Mongeon, P., & Paul-Hus, A. (2016). The journal coverage of Web of Science and Scopus: A
588 comparative analysis. *Scientometrics*, 106(1), 213-228. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1765-5>
- 590 Priem, J., Piwowar, H., & Orr, R. (2022). *OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works,*
591 *authors, venues, institutions, and concepts* (arXiv:2205.01833). arXiv.
592 <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.01833>
- 593 Simard, M.-A., Basson, I., Hare, M., Larivière, V., & Mongeon, P. (2024). The Value of a
594 Diamond: Understanding Global Coverage of Diamond Open Access Journals in Web of
595 Science, Scopus, and OpenAlex to Support an Open Future. *Proceedings of the Annual*
596 *Conference of CAIS / Actes du congrès annuel de l'ACSI*.
597 <https://doi.org/10.29173/cais1845>
- 598 Torres-Salinas, D., Arroyo-Machado, W., & Robinson-García, N. (2025). Principles of
599 Evaluative Bibliometrics in a DORA/CoARA Context (First Edición, January 2025).
600 InluScience Editions. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14672066>
- 601 Torres-Salinas, D., Robinson-García, N., & Jiménez-Contreras, E. (2023). The bibliometric
602 journey towards technological and social change: A review of current challenges and
603 issues. *El Profesional de la información*, e320228.
604 <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2023.mar.28>
- 605 Visser, M., Van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2021). Large-scale comparison of bibliographic
606 data sources: Scopus, Web of Science, Dimensions, Crossref, and Microsoft Academic.
607 *Quantitative Science Studies*, 2(1), 20-41. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00112
- 608 Waltman, L., & Van Eck, N. J. (2012). A new methodology for constructing a publication-level
609 classification system of science. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*
610 *and Technology*, 63(12), 2378-2392. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.22748>
- 611